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Functional Finishing of Viscose Fiber

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to improve the smoothness of the fiber surfaces and improving the fire resistance and antibacterial effect of viscose fiber with antibacterial, flame retardant and protein finishing agent. The viscose fiber had a higher LOI value after flame retardant treatment than the original fiber samples. This demonstrates that flame resistance is improved by using a flame retardant finishing on viscose fiber. The adequacy of the microstructure was researched utilizing electron magnifying scanning (SEM). The antimicrobial properties of the fibre in the coating plate are superior to the phenomenon of chitosan viscose fibers, and the microstructure of the fibrous film under electrical microscope is considered to have a porous cavity structure of the nanofibrillary membrane obtained by the liquid spun. The large specific surface area and a higher type of curling increases the contact area of chitosan and bacteria and can be bonded or adsorbed into the nano-fiber surface, thereby converting the amino group in chitosan into ammonium root ions. More contact bacteria to inhibit bacterial growth. Protein content of cellulose fibers were measured before dyeing and after dyeing, found that the protein content of the cellulose fibers were increased 4% after dyeing & washing. The SEM images showed that longitudinal surfaces of the chitosan viscose fiber, silkworm chrysalis protein viscose fiber, and protein viscose fiber were smooth more than the common viscose fiber and having grooves of different shades.

Keywords

Viscose fiber; Protein, Antibacterial & Flame retardant finishing.

1. Introduction

Lately, individuals' interest for regenerated cellulose fiber has expanded quickly. Notwithstanding its remarkable useful properties, the interest for it is likewise developing quickly. The fundamental attributes of cellulose filaments incorporate variable morphology and variable actual properties, adaptability, great handling properties, adequate liquid vehicle properties and great mechanical properties. As of late, lyocell,

modal, richell and other new assortments were created. Inside dampness content of cellulose fibre is great for human skin. It enjoys the benefit of good turning and open to wearing, more averse to create electricity produced via friction. It can likewise be mixed with regular or any sort of engineered fibre. Not exclusively would it be able to be utilized as a decent one it has a wide scope of employments in dressings as well as in the business, clinical treatment and so forth. However, it likewise has a few inconveniences of low microbiological resistance, high elongation, combustibility, and insufficient staining obstruction.

In modern society, a variety of microorganisms are everywhere, and they are still growing, often affect people's live work and physical health, so it is often used to use antibacterial agents to give the item antibacterial properties. Antibacterial agents are compounds that can stop bacteria, fungus, viruses, and other microbes from growing and reproducing, or kill bacteria. As a result, a variety of effective antibacterial compounds have been investigated for use in viscose fiber modification. Antibacterial agents are divided into three groups depending on their structure, mechanism of action, and source. The most prevalent antimicrobial agents are inorganic, organic, and natural. Organic antibacterial agent often distinguishes according to its molecular weight, including alcohol, phenol, ester, or organic acid, etc.; inorganic antibacterial agents include metal and compounds such as zinc, copper, silver and compounds, etc.; Natural product antibacterial Includes animal and natural minerals, most of which are separated by separation of substances in the organic organism, and the application of chitosan is most widely used. In this paper, chitosan used as an antibacterial agents for modify regenerated cellulose fibre. Chitosan is a chitin by deacemic by deacetylation, as it is non-toxic and non-irritating, good biocompatibility, and broad-spectrum resistance to prepaid people. The amino groups thereof are converted to ammonium ions to effectively inhibit bacterial viruses. And chitosan can be dissolved in a suitable solvent to prepare a filter material having antimicrobial properties, suitable for imparting antimicrobial properties to the filtration material.

In this vein, flame retardant viscose fibre is urgently needed in a variety of implementations for flame suppression and the safety and security of human lives and their belongings. Added material or blending, finishing, unifying or crosslinking, and other procedures can be used to obtain fire resistant viscose fibre and other cellulosic fibres. Added substance or mixing strategy is the easiest method for granting viscose fibre fire retardancy, however there are a few necessities that the added substance fire resistant should satisfy, for instance, similarities with thick turning arrangement, reasonable molecule shape when powerful fire retardants are applied so that spinnerets are not hampered. As of late different creative and fibre surface innovations are being created, and there are large numbers of the lipid layers to eliminate the surface properties and uncover the essence of protein with the substance part of the response. Treatment empowers higher solidness, treatment that can just interface the component of the fiber surface, rather than actually applied to the surface. The surface modify of the protein fiber has long history. Finishing is the most well-known technique for fire security of cellulosic fiber or fabric.

This study is mainly focused on increasing the smoothness of the appearance and improving the fire resistance and antibacterial effect of viscose fiber with antibacterial, flame retardant and protein finishing agent.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials: Common viscose fibers, cashmere protein fibers, chitosan fibers, flame retardant fibers, green tea and contrast fibers were supplied by Shandong Yinying Chemical Fiber Co. Ltd.

2.2 Sample Preparation

2.2.1 Sample Preparation

Experimental preparation: formulated solid, liquid medium, bacterial suspension, instrumentation and tool sterilization

Liquid medium: Take protein, beef cream and sodium chloride and add appropriate amount of distilled water to completely dissolve, adjusting the pH and dispensing. The tapered bottle has a degreasing cotton block and wraps with a rope, and is labeled with a high pressure sterilization pot 120 ° C for 30 minutes.

Solid medium: Add a proper amount of agar in a well liquid medium, and adjust the pH, dispensing, dispensing, and sterilization after complete melting under 80-90 ° C. After taking out, 25 ml into a sterile petri dish, and the solid medium was obtained.

The culture of bacterial suspension: takes a small amount of strain to the culture solution for constant temperature culture to obtain an activated primary coli. Then, the 2nd-generation is obtained from a tapered bottle equipped with a 100 mL of the culture solution to a tapered bottle equipped with a 100 ml of culture. Sterilization of the instrumentation, tools, and cutters were sterilized by ultraviolet sterilization and sterilization.

On the basis of the preparation of the experiment, the prepared second-generation is diluted four times. The first two times were diluted with the culture medium, and the lance was diluted twice. Every time diluted 10 times, up to 10,000 times, each dilution sequentially The predetermined bacteria was prepared according to the ratio of (formercetic liquid: culture fluid or buffer = 1: 9). Then, 5 ml of the final diluted bacterial liquid, 70ml buffer, each tapered bottle, 0.75 g of each conical bottle, plus a blank control group that does not place any fiber, in 25 At a temperature of ° C, 150 r / min oscillated for 24 hours.

After the oscillation is good, each group takes 100 times and 1000 times respectively after each group of two bacteria and the inoculation ring is applied to the plate, and the front vaccination ring is inoculated each time it needs to have before the alcohol lamp. After each tablet is applied, it is sealed and placed in a

biochemical incubator for 24 hours, and the photo count is performed. Depending on the quantity of the colony to determine the advantages and disadvantage resistance.

2.3 Main Performance Detection

2.3.1 Mechanical Performance Test

Single fibre strength were tested by electronic single yarn strength tester YG0006 (Ningbo Textile Instrument Factory) according to Chinese national Standard GB 9997, 14337.

2.3.2 Protein Content Test

Protein content in fibres were measured by the Kjeldahl method, characterized by the fact that KDN-103F automatic nitrogen determinator (Shanghai Lijiang Instrument Co. Ltd, China). Initially it were measured the protein of protein fibers. Then applied the reactive dyeing on those fibers and after dyeing it was washed manually 10 times for each time 5 minutes and dried (water and detergent ratio was 100ml:5ml) and after washing it were tested again.

2.3.3 Moisture Regain Test

Moisture regain of the fibres were measured by Y802A eight basket oven conditional (Changzhou textile machinery, China) according to Chinese national Standard GB / T 6503-2008.

2.3.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy Test

Electron microscope (SEM) scans were performed using the S4800II Cold cathode electric field discharge scanner electron microscope with variable wave voltage of 10 kV to 15 kV (Hitachi, Japan). Acceleration needs attention voltage adjustment required to avoid non-conductive damage.

2.3.5 Anti-flammatory Test

Flame reterdancy of common viscose fibres and treated fabrics were measured by M606B (Shanfang Digital Display Oxygen Index Tester) according to the ASTM D2863-2017a standard.

Figure-1: Anti-flammability test of common viscose fibers (a) & (b) and treated viscose fabric (c) & (d).

3 Results and Discussion

Table 01. Breaking strength and moisture regains of the protein sample fibers.

Sample Fibers	Breaking Strength (cN/dTex)	Moisture Regain (%)
Cashmere protein	3.53	9.43%
Chitosan	1.60	8.80%
Flame retardant	5.09	7.78%
Green tea	2.97	9.07%
Contrast	3.25	9.02%

3.1 Mechanical Performance Test of Cellulose Fibers

It does rely upon the level of crystallinity, the level of polymerization and the direction of macromolecules in glasslike and indistinct districts of fibers. It can be seen from the Table-01 of mechanical performance that there were highest strength of flame retardant fiber and the lowest one was chitosan, which indicated that the strength of the flame retardant fibers were more than other sample fibers.

3.2 Moisture Regain

The moisture regains of cellulose fibers were shown in Table-01 of moisture regain. It's seen that moisture regains of cashmere protein was higher than others those cellulose fibers and green tea & contrast fibers were almost similar, which indicated that hygroscopicity of cashmere protein was better than other sample fibers.

3.3 Protein Content Test

The nitrogen content of cellulose fiber is commonly used to determine its protein composition. The protein content of cellulose fibers was examined before and after dyeing, and it was discovered that the fiber had 7% protein after dyeing and washing (5 times), but only 3% before dying. After dyeing, the protein content of cellulose fibers increased. After dyeing with reactive dyes, the nitrogen content of protein fibers increased considerably. This is due to the fact that reactive dyes frequently include nitrogen.

3.4 Surface Morphology

It can be seen from the SEM images that longitudinal surfaces of the chitosan viscose fiber, silkworm chrysalis protein viscose fiber, and protein viscose fiber (A&B) were smooth more than the common viscose fiber and having grooves of different shades.

Figure-2: SEM images of common viscose fibers (a), silkworm chrysalis protein viscose fibers (b), protein viscose fibers sample (A&B) (c) and (d), and 10% chitosan viscose fibers (e) respectively.

3.5 Anti-bacterial Performance:

Combined with the antibacterial performance of the fiber film in the coated plate is better than the phenomenon of chitosan viscose fiber, the microscopic structure of the fiber film under electron microscopy is considered to be that the nano-fiber membrane made of liquid spray spinning has a multi-porous cavity structure, a large specific surface area and a network structure with high curl, which increases the contact area between chitosan and bacteria and can bind or adsorb bacteria to the surface of nano-fibers, so that the amino group in chitosan can be converted into ammonium ions and can contact bacteria more to inhibit the growth of bacteria.

3.6 Anti-flammability:

Figure-3: Influence of flame retardant finishing on viscose fiber.

The viscose fiber had a higher LOI value after flame retardant treatment than the original fiber samples. This demonstrates that flame resistance is improved by using a flame retardant finishing on viscose fiber. The limiting oxygen index value of viscose fiber were $>25\%$, $>27.6\%$, $>32.8\%$ and after the flame retardant finishing $<34.1\%$, $>30\%$, >32 respectively. So this result showed flame resistance effect increased of the fiber after the flame retardant finishing.

4 Conclusion

The focal point of our research was to apply various surface treatments onto financially accessible viscose fiber to improve the surface smoothness, antibacterial impact and fire resistance properties of fibers. It can be seen from the Table-01 of mechanical performance that there were highest strength of flame retardant fibre and the lowest one was chitosan, which indicated that the strength of the flame retardant fibres were more than other sample fibres. The cashmere fibres had high moisture regain and green tea & contrast fibres had almost similar, which indicated that hygroscopicity of cashmere protein was better than other sample fibres. After modify, it's seen that longitudinal surfaces of the chitosan viscose fibre, silkworm chrysalis protein viscose fibre, and protein viscose fibre were smooth more than the common viscose fibre and having grooves of different shades. Protein content of cellulose fibre after dyeing was increased 4%, it was 3% before dyeing and after dyeing & washing 7%. The nitrogen content of protein fibres increased significantly after dyeing with reactive dyes. This is because reactive dyes often contain nitrogen. The antimicrobial properties of the fibre in the coating plate are superior to the phenomenon of chitosan viscose fibres, and the microstructure of the fibrous film under electrical microscope is considered to have a porous cavity structure of the nano-fiber membrane obtained by the liquid spun. The large specific surface area and a higher type of curling increases the contact area of chitosan and bacteria and can be bonded or adsorbed into the nano-fiber surface, thereby converting the amino group in chitosan into ammonium root ions. More contact bacteria to inhibit bacterial growth. The viscose fibre had a higher LOI value after flame retardant treatment than the original fibre samples. This demonstrates that flame resistance is improved by using a flame retardant finishing on viscose fibre. These new types of viscose fiber are expected to fill a market niche with increasing demand in the future.

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